
Load Frequency Control of a Single Area Power System Using Type-1 Fuzzy Controller

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ABSTRACT— Load frequency control problem is considered as one of the most important issues in the design and operation of power systems. Due to lack of good efficiency in parameters variation conditions, working conditions of system and non-linear factors, a simple PI controller is not suitable in industrial applications. Instead, fuzzy controllers can be used in order to enhance the performances of the systems. In this paper, the use of the optimized type-1 fuzzy logic controller is proposed to solve the load frequency control problem. To the best of our knowledge, fuzzy type-1 controller in order to solve load-frequency control problem, has not been investigated so far. The proposed controller has good performance and is capable to solve the load-frequency control problem in conditions of wide variations of system parameters and nonlinear factors such as generation rate constraint. Simulation results show that the optimized fuzzy controller proposed in this paper exhibits better performance compared to PI controller in damping of system deviations.

Keywords – Load Frequency Control, Single area power system, Type-I Fuzzy Controller

1. INTRODUCTION:

Load-Frequency (L-F) control [1] is an important task in electrical power system design and operation. Since the load demand varies without any prior schedule, the power generation is expected to overcome these variations without any voltage and frequency instabilities. Therefore voltage and frequency controllers are required to maintain the generated power quality[2] in order to supply constant voltage and frequency to the utility grid. The frequency Control is done by load-frequency controllers [3], which deals with the control of generator loadings depending on the frequency. Many researchers have been done and a different approach has been proposed over the past decades regarding the load-frequency control of single and multi area power systems.

The problem of output active power control of a power system in response to power system frequency changes and between regional powers of system lines in a specified range is known as the load-frequency control problem. For optimal performance and optimal operation of power systems, the frequency changes must be maintained within certain limits. Many process control systems, such as computers, are sensitive to changes in the frequency and their operation is impaired. For such systems, their frequency must be regulated and controlled. Therefore, An adequate supplementary controller to regulate and prevent frequency deviations must be used in the main control center.

The main purpose of designing load-frequency controllers is to ensure the stable and reliable operation of power systems. Since the components of a power system are non linear, a linearized model around an operating point is used in the design process of L-F